

CO-CREATING BEHAVIOURAL CHANGE TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART FOOD SYSTEMS

D 5.3 Capacity building activities for policy makers

June 2026

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Terms	Definition
AEIDL	European Association for Innovation in Local Development
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
AUA	Agricultural University of Athens
BEATLES	Behavioural Change Towards Climate-Smart Agriculture (https://beatles-project.eu/)
BM	Business Model
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CCW	Co-Creation Workshop
CoR	Committee of the Regions
CSA	Climate-Smart Agriculture
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development – European Commission
DG CLIMA	Directorate-General for Climate Action – European Commission
EC	European Commission
EESC	European Economic and Social Committee
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EP	European Parliament
ELIF	European Local Innovation Forum
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
JRC	Joint Research Centre
INTIA	Navarre Institute for Agrifood Technologies and Infrastructures (in Spanish: Instituto Navarro de Tecnologías e Infraestructuras Agroalimentarias)
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
NRPP	National and Regional Partnership Plans
PB	Policy Brief
RENURE	REcovered Nitrogen from manURE
SEI	Stockholm Environment Institute
UC	Use Case
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

BEATLES is a Horizon Europe project running from 2022 to 2026 that supports the transition towards Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) by generating evidence on behavioural, systemic and governance factors influencing the uptake of climate-smart practices and technologies. Within this framework, Work Package 5 (WP5) focuses on translating project findings into policy recommendations, practical tools and capacity-building activities for policy makers, policy advisors and other actors involved in agricultural and food-system transitions.

Deliverable D5.3 – Capacity-building activities for policy makers documents the mutual learning and capacity-building actions implemented under Work Package 5 (WP5), in line with the Description of the Action (Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). WP5 focuses on translating BEATLES findings into policy recommendations, tools and support mechanisms for public authorities and advisory actors.

In this context, D5.3 reports on the organisation and results of a series of EU-level multi-actor workshops and complementary activities designed to engage policy makers and policy-relevant stakeholders, support knowledge transfer, and enhance their capacity to design, implement and evaluate policies for Climate-Smart Agriculture.

The deliverable **demonstrates the achievement of Task 5.4 Mutual learning and capacity building for policy action objectives** by evidencing stakeholder engagement, learning processes and policy dialogue activities, as well as their contribution to the uptake, dissemination and exploitation of BEATLES policy outputs. These activities were connected with the wider work of the project, including the co-creation processes developed with the BEATLES Use Cases, which provided important insights into the practical barriers, needs and enabling conditions affecting CSA transitions in different territorial and sectoral contexts. In this way, the policy dialogue developed under WP5 was informed by both project-level research outputs and stakeholder experiences gathered throughout the project.

It reports the mutual learning and activities carried out under Task 5.4 of the BEATLES project **running from Month 12 (June 2023) to Month 48 (June 2026)**.

The deliverable focuses on the EU Multi-Actor Working Group, which was established as a structured space for dialogue between BEATLES partners and external stakeholders with expertise in policy, advisory services, research, innovation and agri-food systems. The Working Group supported policy learning by helping participants discuss BEATLES findings, assess their relevance for policy diagnosis, design, implementation and monitoring, and translate evidence into more actionable policy messages. Its methodology combined mutual learning formats, systematic documentation, participation and feedback data, and ethical safeguards for stakeholder engagement.

The **EU Multi-Actor Working Group was implemented through three online pan-European workshops and one final policy session**. The first workshop, held in May 2024, focused on discussing and externally assessing early BEATLES findings in relation to CAP reform and Climate-Smart Agriculture. The second workshop, held in January 2025, used a policy hackathon format to support the co-design of solutions and policy recommendations for expanding CSA towards 2030 and 2040. The third workshop, held in May 2025, explored fairness in EU agri-food policy and considered how fairness could be translated into practical steps for policy design, implementation and evaluation. The final policy session, held on 2 June 2026, presented and discussed BEATLES policy recommendations and tools, with a focus on their potential application and scaling through current and upcoming EU policy instruments.

In addition to the workshops, **D5.3 reports complementary capacity-building activities that supported the wider policy relevance and visibility of BEATLES outputs.** These included contributions to EU consultations and policy processes, policy briefs, exchanges with other BEATLES work packages research and dissemination activities, and synergies with relevant Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, EU networks and related initiatives.

The activities contributed positively to the project's capacity-building objectives. **In total, over 200 relevant actors were engaged** through D5.3-related workshops, and 97% of feedback respondents reported feeling better informed after the three online workshops. The Working Group exceeded the target of engaging more than 20 policy makers, **with 47 policy makers and policy-relevant actors participating across the workshop series.** Beyond direct participation, many more stakeholders were informed through the dissemination of results, the sharing of information with national CAP Networks, and outreach through multiplier organisations and EU-level networks. This wider communication process increased the visibility and reach of BEATLES policy messages and capacity-building results.

Stakeholder engagement extended beyond the workshop series through a comprehensive policy consultation process. This process included **nine interviews** with UC leaders and national policy experts, a dedicated **consultation on CAP Use Cases findings** that gathered **eight national responses**, and an expert **consultation supporting the fairness assessment, through which twelve experts** provided detailed qualitative feedback.

From an exploitation perspective, D5.3 is aligned with the project-level BEATLES Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D6.7). It does not introduce new D5.3-specific Key Exploitable Results (KERs), but explains how WP5 policy-oriented outputs contribute to three project-level KERs: KER3 - Methodology and implementation of co-creation activities within BEATLES, KER5 - Farm Advice Guide: fair value propositions, business models portfolio and other main outcomes, and KER6 - Policy recommendations and tools. The strongest contribution is to KER6, through the BEATLES policy recommendations, the CSA Policy Toolkit, policy briefs, consultation inputs and related policy-support materials. D5.3 also contributes to KER3 through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group as a co-creation and policy-learning process, and to KER5 by supporting the dissemination of policy-relevant insights to advisory actors, farm-support organisations and multiplier networks.

Overall, D5.3 shows that the EU Multi-Actor Working Group acted as a bridge between BEATLES research outputs and their potential policy uptake. The activities reported helped validate findings, support mutual learning, strengthen capacity among policy-relevant actors and create practical routes for future use.

1. Introduction

BEATLES (*Behavioural Change Towards Climate-Smart Agriculture*) is a Horizon Europe project running from 2022 to 2026 and coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA). The project brings together 17 partner organisations across Europe to support the transition towards Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) and smart farming technologies. It does so by generating evidence on behavioural, systemic and governance factors that influence the uptake of CSA, co-creating policy options, and supporting their use by relevant actors across agri-food systems.

Within this framework, **Work Package 5 (Transition through policy recommendations and tools)** focuses on **translating project findings into policy recommendations, practical tools and capacity-building actions.** Its purpose is to support public authorities

and policy advisors in designing, implementing and evaluating policies that can enable behavioural change and improve the uptake of climate-smart practices and technologies.

In particular, **Task 5.4, Mutual learning and capacity building for policy action**, provides the basis for this work. Running from Month 12 (December 2023) to Month 48 (June 2026) and led by AEIDL in cooperation with the partners coordinating the use cases (AgriFood Lithuania DIH, Naturland, INTIA, Food & Biocluster Denmark, and DELPHY), the task supports knowledge transfer and exploitation **through a series of international multi-actor workshops**. These workshops are addressed to policy makers and policy advisors, and are designed to discuss project findings, test their policy relevance, and support the transfer, adaptation, and replication of BEATLES approaches, recommendations, guides, practice abstracts, and other relevant outputs.

In this context, Deliverable **D5.3, Capacity-building activities for policy makers**, documents the mutual learning and capacity-building activities carried out through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group. The Working Group was established as a structured platform for dialogue between BEATLES partners and external stakeholders with expertise in policy, advisory services, research, innovation and agri-food transitions. Its role was to create a space where project findings could be discussed, validated and translated into more actionable policy messages.

The added value of D5.3 lies in showing how BEATLES policy outputs were brought closer to potential users. The deliverable therefore focuses on three connected dimensions: **capacity building, policy learning and exploitation**. First, it describes how the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops helped participants engage with BEATLES evidence and reflect on its relevance for policy design, implementation and evaluation. Second, it reports how the discussions contributed to the refinement and contextualisation of policy-oriented outputs developed under WP5. Third, it identifies how these outputs can continue to be used after the project through practical exploitation pathways.

The BEATLES project adopts a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) consistent with Horizon Europe Cluster 6 requirements, which emphasise interactive, transdisciplinary research and innovation processes involving actors with complementary knowledge and expertise (European Commission, n.d.; EU CAP Network, n.d.). Within this framework, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group can be understood as a structured platform enabling co-creation, mutual learning and the validation of policy-oriented outputs throughout the project lifecycle. This reflects the broader AKIS perspective, where innovation is seen as a systemic and collaborative process requiring continuous interaction between researchers, policy makers, advisors and practitioners to ensure relevance and uptake (EU SCAR AKIS, 2019). Empirical studies confirm that such multi-actor partnerships enhance the applicability and impact of results by integrating scientific and practical knowledge and fostering co-ownership of outcomes (Guerrero-Ocampo et al., 2022; Fieldsend et al., 2021). Moreover, evidence from Horizon-type projects highlights that effective multi-actor engagement—through iterative dialogue, stakeholder inclusion and facilitation—supports knowledge exchange and strengthens the link between research and policy (Feo et al., 2021; Conway et al., 2024). In BEATLES, this approach underpins the design of capacity-building activities and policy dialogue, ensuring that project outputs are grounded in real policy needs and positioned for uptake within EU and national governance frameworks.

The EU Multi-Actor Working Group also supported the wider policy ambition of BEATLES by linking project results to ongoing European debates on the future of agricultural and food systems. In particular, the workshops and related activities addressed issues relevant to the **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Farm to Fork Strategy, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, climate policy, fairness in agri-food value chains, and the post-2027 policy framework**. This helped position BEATLES results within real policy discussions and

increased their relevance for public authorities, policy advisors and other actors involved in agricultural transition processes.

Through a series of pan-European workshops, the Working Group provided opportunities for policy makers, researchers, advisors, innovators, civil society organisations and other stakeholders to **discuss implementation challenges, assess transferability, identify trade-offs and explore the conditions needed for the uptake of CSA** in different national and regional contexts. In this way, the workshops contributed not only to dissemination, but also to mutual learning, policy reflection and early exploitation of BEATLES results.

In addition to reporting these activities, D5.3 presents the **exploitation pathway for the policy-oriented outputs linked to the** EU Multi-Actor Working Group. This includes the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), their target users, potential uptake routes, and the actions needed to support their continued visibility, accessibility and use beyond the lifetime of the BEATLES project.

Following this introduction, **the document is structured as follows**. Section 2 explains the methodology used to organise, documents and assesses the capacity-building process. Section 3 presents the EU Multi-Actor Working Group and related capacity-building activities, including how the Working Group was formed, how the four workshops were implemented, and how complementary policy-support activities such as EU consultation contributions, policy briefs and links with other BEATLES work packages supported the overall process. Section 4 sets out the exploitation and sustainability pathway for the policy-oriented outputs, ensuring alignment with the BEATLES Exploitation and Sustainability Plan. Section 5 addresses the main risks, mitigation measures, and contingency actions needed to ensure continuity. Finally, Section 6 summarises the main conclusions and highlights recommendations for further policy uptake.

2. Methodology

Deliverable 5.3 *Capacity-building activities for policy makers* follows a process-oriented methodology designed to document how BEATLES supported mutual learning, policy reflection and capacity building through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group. The approach focused on creating structured spaces where project findings could be **presented, discussed, tested and translated into more usable policy messages** for public authorities, policy advisors and other actors involved in the transition towards Climate-Smart Agriculture.

The methodology followed a progressive sequence. First, the process built on the wider stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities carried out in BEATLES, particularly those developed through T1.3 with the Use Cases, which helped identify relevant policy themes, implementation challenges and stakeholder profiles. This was complemented by a stakeholder mapping exercise to identify relevant actors across policy, research, advisory services, civil society and agri-food networks. Around 1,600 actors were mapped as potential contributors to the process. Second, targeted engagement was used to invite key stakeholders according to the topic of each session. Third, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops were organised, creating a space for exchange with policy makers, experts and practitioners. Finally, feedback was collected after each session to refine the process and support follow-up activities.

Figure 1 provides a visual overview of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group methodology. It shows how the process moved from stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement to workshop delivery, feedback collection and capacity-building outcomes.

Figure 1. Methodological approach of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group

The methodology was designed not only to organise workshops, but also to create a dialogue process for policy uptake. Several sources fed into the process, including BEATLES use cases, national and EU-level experts, interviews with Managing Authorities, Paying Agencies, advisors and evaluators, business models and value propositions developed within the project, and an online consultation on fairness. These inputs helped frame the discussions around practical policy needs.

The dialogue process then supported the development and refinement of several WP5 outputs, including BEATLES policy recommendations, three CSA policy tools, policy briefs, contributions to EU consultations, workshop reports and supporting materials. In particular, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group fed into two major outputs: the BEATLES policy recommendations, and the CSA policy toolkit. These outputs are presented in detail in [D5.1, Policy Recommendations and Tools](#), which provides the full set of policy recommendations, technical fiches and practical tools developed to support Climate-Smart Agriculture policy design, implementation and monitoring

Figure 2 summarises how BEATLES inputs, dialogue activities and outputs contributed to policy uptake. It shows how evidence from the project and external stakeholders was channelled through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group process and translated into policy recommendations, tools, briefs and other resources.

Figure 2. Progressive dialogue process for policy uptake

All this dialogue and engagement process is ultimately reflected in the project’s policy uptake activities and in the development of two key deliverables under Work Package 5. On the one hand, **it contributes to Deliverable 5.1, Policy Recommendations and Tools (M48)**, both in its report version and in its web-based environment version. On the other hand, it also feeds directly into the present deliverable, **Deliverable 5.3, Capacity Building Activities for Policy Makers (M48)**.

The objective was to move BEATLES evidence from discussion to policy uptake. To do this, each workshop was designed around a specific step in the uptake pathway: testing early findings, co-designing policy options, deepening the discussion on fairness, and assessing how the final recommendations and tools could be used in practice. Table 1 summarises this progression and shows how each workshop contributed to the overall capacity-building and policy-learning objectives of Task 5.4.

Table 1. Overview of the mutual learning formats used in the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops

Workshop & date	Main focus	Mutual learning format	Methodological purpose
1st workshop (23 May 2024)	Discussion and external assessment of BEATLES findings on CSA uptake, with a focus on CAP reform, EU-level policy analysis, Use Case evidence and emerging policy needs.	Working groups combined with plenary discussion under Chatham House rules .	To assess whether the early BEATLES policy findings reflected real implementation challenges for CSA uptake, gather feedback on CAP interventions and financial incentives relevant to the five Use Cases, and identify policy needs to inform the development of EU-level policy recommendations.
2nd workshop (13 January 2025)	Co-design of solutions and policy recommendations to support the expansion of CSA towards 2030 and 2040.	Policy hackathon where participants worked in expert pairs on challenge statements and	To move from analysis to solution-oriented reflection and support the joint development of practical policy options and recommendations for scaling up CSA.

<p>3rd workshop (19 May 2025)</p>	<p>Exploration of the notion of fairness in EU agri-food policy.</p>	<p>collaborative solution-building.</p>	<p>Expert presentations, breakout group exercise, and plenary discussion</p>	<p>To explore fairness as a multidimensional policy principle and translate expert recommendations into actionable steps for policy design, implementation and evaluation.</p>
<p>4th workshop (2 June 2026)</p>	<p>Discussion of BEATLES policy recommendations and tools, and their potential application and scaling through current and upcoming EU policy instruments.</p>	<p>Presentation of BEATLES policy outputs followed by an expert roundtable with representatives of EU institutions and relevant organisations.</p>	<p>To assess how the BEATLES policy recommendations and CSA policy toolkit could be applied, scaled and connected to current and upcoming EU policy instruments., including the 2028–2034 period.</p>	

These formats ensured both continuity and progression across the EU Multi-Actor Working Group process. The first workshop introduced the BEATLES approach and tested AEIDL’s early policy analysis against real implementation challenges. The second workshop built on this basis by encouraging participants to **co-design concrete policy responses** through a more solution-oriented format. The third workshop broadened the discussion by focusing on **fairness as a key principle for the future design and implementation of agri-food policies**. The fourth workshop brought the process closer to **uptake and exploitation** by discussing how **BEATLES recommendations and tools** could inform current and upcoming EU policy instruments.

This sequence strengthened the capacity-building role of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group by helping participants move from understanding BEATLES findings to reflecting on how these findings could be interpreted, adapted and used in real policy contexts. The activities were also organised at a strategically relevant moment, against the backdrop of wider discussions on CAP simplification, the post-2027 CAP, and the evolving architecture of national and regional policy planning, including the proposed National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs). This timing increased the relevance of the workshop process for policy actors and helped situate BEATLES outputs within current institutional and strategic debates.

The outputs of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops were captured through a systematic documentation process. Agendas, background materials, **highlights reports, presentations, session recordings, participation records** and **feedback** forms were used to capture both the content presented and the main insights emerging from the discussions. These sources provided a consistent evidence base for documenting the capacity-building process, assessing participation and outreach, and identifying insights relevant for subsequent WP5 activities, including policy recommendations, policy briefs, consultation inputs and future uptake.

Participation and feedback data were also used to assess the contribution of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group to the objectives of Task 5.4. Registration and attendance records helped document participant profiles, including institutional background, geographical coverage and stakeholder category. Post-event feedback forms captured participants’ views on the relevance, usefulness and quality of the activities, including whether they felt better informed and whether the workshops helped them identify policy aspects or implementation challenges they had not previously considered. The results of this assessment are presented in Section 3.5 on the contribution to project KPIs.

The methodology also incorporated ethical safeguards for participation in the EU Multi-Actor Working Group. Participants were informed about the purpose of the activities, the

expected use of their contributions, confidentiality arrangements, data protection provisions and their right to withdraw. Consent was collected through the expression of interest and registration forms, including confirmation of confidentiality arrangements, permission for follow-up contact where applicable, and consent for the documentation of information generated during the activities, while maintaining participant confidentiality.

Participation was voluntary and limited to adults engaging in a professional capacity. The Chatham House Rule was applied where appropriate to encourage open exchange, and working group discussions were not recorded in full. Participants could remain off-camera or request the editing or removal of identifiable material where applicable. Personal data and participation records were managed in line with GDPR requirements, the project privacy policy and AEIDL's internal procedures.

Overall, this methodological approach ensured that the Working Group functioned not only as a dissemination channel, but also as a structured, inclusive and ethical process for policy support and mutual learning. It allowed BEATLES findings to be discussed with relevant policy makers and advisors, helped produce reusable materials, and provided evidence to assess how the activities contributed to capacity building and future uptake.

3. EU Multi-Actor Working Group

3.1 Objectives and role within BEATLES

Under Task 5.4, *Mutual learning and capacity building for policy action*, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group was used as a practical testing and feedback mechanism for BEATLES policy outputs. Its purpose was to check whether emerging project findings, recommendations and tools were relevant, understandable and usable for actors involved in Climate-Smart Agriculture policy design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation.

Rather than functioning only as a dissemination forum, the Working Group provided structured input at different stages of WP5. The first workshop tested early policy findings from EU-level analysis and the five Use Cases. The second workshop supported the co-design of policy options for scaling CSA towards 2030 and 2040. The third workshop examined how fairness could be translated into practical policy design, implementation and evaluation. The final policy session focused on the uptake of the BEATLES recommendations and CSA Policy Toolkit in current and future EU policy frameworks.

The Working Group therefore played an operational role in the preparation, implementation and progressive updating of WP5 policy work. It helped prepare the policy dialogue by identifying relevant stakeholders and policy themes, supported implementation through structured workshops and expert exchanges, and enabled continuous updating through feedback forms, participation data, workshop reports and follow-up activities.

In this way, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group helped refine WP5 outputs while also generating evidence for capacity building. The discussions and supporting materials were used to document how policy-relevant actors engaged with BEATLES results and how these results could be further adapted for policy uptake. The formal exploitation pathway of these outputs is addressed in Section 4.

3.2 Stakeholder mapping and engagement

The stakeholder mapping process aimed to ensure that discussions reflected real implementation needs, institutional realities and current policy debates linked to CSA, the CAP and the future post-2027 governance framework.

Building on the methodological approach developed under Deliverable 5.1 and the wider WP5 activities, the stakeholder engagement strategy combined stakeholder mapping, targeted invitations, expert interviews, online consultations, validation exercises, policy workshops and dissemination activities. Rather than functioning as a one-off consultation exercise, engagement evolved progressively throughout the project and helped shape the content, methodology and policy orientation of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group process.

In total, **around 1,600 stakeholders were mapped as potential contributors to the Working Group and broader WP5 policy activities.** Stakeholders were categorised according to their thematic expertise, institutional role, governance level and relevance to specific policy discussions. The mapping focused primarily on actors involved in CAP governance, implementation and advisory systems, including Managing Authorities, Paying Agencies, ministries, CAP Strategic Plan teams, evaluators, advisors, researchers, EU institutions, national CAP networks, civil society organisations, farmers' organisations, value-chain actors and innovation networks. Particular attention was given to actors working on policy areas linked to climate action, biodiversity, Farm to Fork implementation, sustainable food systems, digitalisation, rural development and behavioural change.

The engagement process was implemented progressively through different phases and activities. An initial **targeted outreach process mobilised approximately 250 stakeholders for the first EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop** held in May 2024. The stakeholder database was then updated and used to support subsequent workshops, consultations, interviews, targeted exchanges and follow-up communications. Stakeholders were progressively mobilised according to the thematic focus and methodological design of each activity. Detailed participation figures and stakeholder profiles for each workshop are presented in Section 3.3.

Continuous engagement also took place beyond the workshops, particularly through related WP5 activities feeding into D5.1. Selected experts, use case representatives and national implementation actors were involved through interviews, an online consultation, ad hoc exchanges and validation activities. These interactions helped maintain continuity between the different stages of the process and ensured that the Working Group remained connected to practical policy, advisory and implementation perspectives.

Progressively, the number of participants evolved towards a smaller and more targeted group, reflecting the specific methodological approach adopted for each stage of the process. The workshop series was intentionally designed to move from a broader webinar-style dialogue towards more specialised and interactive formats, including a policy hackathon and, finally, a smaller expert policy group. This progressive reduction in participant numbers responded to the need to facilitate deeper exchanges, collaborative work and more operational policy discussions as the process evolved from general policy reflection towards co-creation and expert-level dialogue.

In total, **more than 200 stakeholders directly participated in the three EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops organised between 2024 and 2025 and the Final Policy Event in 2026.** The process prioritised the participation of actors with recognised expertise and institutional relevance rather than large-scale outreach, ensuring meaningful dialogue and actionable policy feedback.

Beyond the workshops themselves, stakeholder engagement also contributed to broader policy outreach and dissemination activities. Contacts generated through the mapping exercise and Working Group process were used to disseminate policy briefs, workshop reports, consultation contributions, factsheets and policy tools developed within WP5. BEATLES outputs and policy reflections were also presented and discussed in multiple European policy forums and institutional events, including activities linked to the European Committee of the Regions, the European Economic and Social Committee, the European CAP Network, ENASP, ELIF and CODECS.

Participation in the Working Group workshops was based **on a targeted invitation process**. This was part of the preparation phase of each activity and aimed to involve stakeholders who could contribute substantively to the discussions, provide relevant policy or implementation expertise, and connect BEATLES findings with current institutional and strategic processes.

As a result, stakeholder engagement supported not only participation in the workshops, but also the policy relevance, quality and long-term exploitation potential of the outputs generated through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group.

3.3 Working Group workshops

The EU Multi-Actor Working Group was implemented **during Years 2 to 4** of the BEATLES project as a structured process of policy dialogue, mutual learning, and early exploitation of results. Rather than being organised as a one-off activity, it developed progressively through three online pan-European workshops and a final policy session targeting policy makers, policy advisors and other stakeholders involved in policy support, research, innovation and agri-food transitions.

This phased approach allowed the EU Multi-Actor Working Group to evolve from an initial space for presenting and validating BEATLES findings into a more operational platform for co-designing recommendations, discussing implementation challenges and exploring fairness in agri-food systems and assessing the future use of BEATLES policy recommendations and tools.

Across the four activities, AEIDL facilitated exchanges between BEATLES partners and external stakeholders to discuss, review and refine the project's policy-oriented outputs. **The overview below presents the sessions held**, together with their objectives, participant profiles, preparation and organisation, speakers and contributions, main materials and outputs generated, challenges encountered, and their contribution to capacity building and early uptake.

3.3.1 First EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop

The first EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop aimed to test early BEATLES policy findings against real implementation challenges for CSA uptake. The discussion centred on AEIDL's initial analysis of EU policy frameworks, CAP Strategic Plans, public support for 25 CSA practices in the five Use Cases, and emerging policy needs related to financial incentives, technical support and market conditions.

The workshop served mainly as a validation and orientation exercise. Its main objective was to assess whether the initial findings reflected the barriers, opportunities and practical implementation challenges experienced by policy actors and stakeholders, and to gather external feedback that could inform the development of BEATLES policy recommendations. It was also framed as part of the wider BEATLES co-creation process,

helping to explore how project findings could be discussed at EU level and translated into actionable policy messages.

Date: 23 May 2024

Format: Online

Participants profile: 63 attendees from 21 countries

- Researchers: 24
- EU Institutions (DG AGRI, DG CLIMA, JRC, Evaluation Helpdesk, EP): 10
- Public authority/policy makers (SK, IE, LT, MT, DK, ES): 9
- Advisor/Innovation broker/intermediary: 6
- NGO (such as EIT Food, EEB or European Climate Foundation): 5
- EU-funded projects: 3
- Agri-food industry, business and rural entrepreneurs: 2
- Civil Society Organisation: 2
- Others: 2

Figure 3. First EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop by typology of stakeholders

The participant profile showed strong policy relevance. Most participants reported **experience in policy design, implementation, monitoring and/or evaluation** in the field of agriculture and food, with 59 respondents indicating relevant experience and 7 reporting no such experience. In terms of thematic expertise, participants showed the strongest **familiarity with agriculture (63) and environment (55)**, followed by **climate-related topics (37)**. More limited, but still relevant, experience was identified in **digitalisation (18) and rural issues (17)**.

Preparation and organisation: The workshop was prepared through a targeted stakeholder engagement process building on the BEATLES stakeholder mapping exercise and the policy-relevant insights emerging from the Use Cases. As this was the first meeting of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group, particular effort was devoted to introducing the objectives of the BEATLES project, presenting the rationale of the policy dialogue process, and establishing a diverse and balanced group of participants. Stakeholders were selected based on their expertise in Climate-Smart Agriculture, CAP implementation, agricultural advisory services, research, innovation and policy evaluation. The preparation process combined the activation of existing stakeholder networks with personalised invitations, bilateral exchanges and individual meetings to secure the participation of key experts from both EU and national levels. The agenda was designed to familiarise participants with the project while gathering initial feedback on emerging findings and policy challenges related to CSA uptake.

Challenges encountered: One of the main challenges was establishing a new multi-actor policy dialogue platform and attracting stakeholders who were not yet familiar with the BEATLES project. Considerable efforts were required to identify and engage experts capable of bridging policy and practice perspectives, combining knowledge of national agricultural realities, Climate-Smart Agriculture approaches and CAP implementation. Ensuring a balanced representation of different Member States and stakeholder categories while maintaining a manageable and interactive group size also required targeted outreach and follow-up. Another challenge was translating early-stage project findings into discussion materials that were sufficiently concrete and relevant for policy experts to provide meaningful feedback.

Speakers and contributions: The agenda combined BEATLES project inputs with external policy and technical perspectives. **Marilena Gemtou** from AUA introduced the BEATLES project. **Gijs Schilthuis** from DG AGRI presented EU policy perspectives for agriculture. **Blanca Casares** from AEIDL presented policy insights from BEATLES, while **Irene Guerrero** from the Joint Research Centre addressed farm-practice classification for CAP interventions. **Iiri Raa** from EIP-AGRI contributed with a presentation on smart farm practices and innovation. Together, these contributions helped frame the discussion around CAP implementation, CSA uptake and the practical policy conditions needed to support innovation in agriculture.

Materials:

- [Highlights report](#)
- [Presentations](#)
- [Recordings](#)
- [News item](#)

Results, policy learning and uptake: The first workshop helped participants examine the evolving policy framework surrounding CSA, particularly in relation to CAP reform, implementation challenges and the role of behavioural and governance factors in supporting CSA uptake. Through the presentations, discussions and breakout exchanges, participants were able to reflect on policy gaps, compare implementation realities across countries, and identify barriers and enabling conditions affecting the transferability of CSA practices and policy instruments.

The workshop also helped connect research evidence with practical policy design and implementation needs, while increasing awareness of how BEATLES results could support future CAP-related discussions and policy processes. In addition, the feedback collected helped identify which policy messages resonated most strongly with policy audiences, which recommendations required further refinement, and which themes deserved deeper exploration in subsequent workshops. In this way, the workshop functioned not only as a dissemination activity, but also as an initial bridge between BEATLES research outputs, stakeholder validation processes and future policy uptake and exploitation pathways.

3.3.2 Second EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop

The second EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop aimed to **co-design solutions and EU policy recommendations** to support the expansion of Climate-Smart Agriculture towards 2030 and 2040. It built on the [Political Guidelines](#) for the new European Commission, the **Strategic Dialogue for the Future of Agriculture**, and the emerging **Vision for Agriculture and Food**. It also sought to test BEATLES findings with external experts and policy practitioners through a collaborative **policy hackathon**.

The **policy hackathon format** was designed to move beyond problem identification and foster the co-creation of actionable policy solutions. After introductory presentations on BEATLES results and the EU policy landscape, participants engaged in a structured collaborative exercise focused on two core challenge statements: one addressing support for farmers in adopting CSA practices, and another focusing on how policymakers can design and implement effective CSA-related policies.

The outputs generated during the hackathon informed several subsequent project activities. In particular, they contributed to the refinement of the BEATLES policy recommendations, provided additional insights for the development of the CSA Policy Toolkit, and helped validate policy priorities identified across the Use Cases.

Participants were organised into small working groups (2–4 participants), ensuring a balanced mix of expertise. The thematic areas were defined on the basis of participants' professional profiles, areas of expertise and relevance to the BEATLES policy work. This allowed the discussion to cover different dimensions of CSA uptake, including rural development, agricultural economics, innovation systems, agri-environmental policy, governance, climate adaptation and mitigation, behavioural science, organic farming, biodiversity and technology transfer.

Each group followed the same working structure: defining key messages, contextualising the challenge, building on existing knowledge, developing concrete policy recommendations and assessing the feasibility of implementation by 2030 and 2040.

Each group was assigned a thematic focus reflecting its members' expertise:

- Group 1 – Rural Regeneration and EU Policy.
- Group 2 – Agricultural Economics and Innovation Systems.
- Group 3 – Agri-environmental Policy and Ecosystem Services.
- Group 4 – Sustainable Food Systems and Stakeholder Engagement.
- Group 5 – Governance, Policy Planning and Decision-Making.
- Group 6 – Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation.
- Group 7 – Behavioural Science and Consumer Engagement.
- Group 8 – Organic Farming and Sectoral Innovation.
- Group 9 – Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Technology Transfer.
- Group 10 – Governance and Rural Social Innovation.
- Group 11 – Biodiversity, Landscape Management and Soil Health.

This thematic clustering facilitated focused discussions while enabling a rapid assessment of the diversity of expertise across groups.

The hackathon concluded with a plenary session where each group presented its outputs, allowing for peer feedback, validation, and refinement of ideas. This iterative process supported collective learning and strengthened the quality and relevance of the proposed solutions.

Date: **13 January 2025**

Format: **Online**

Participants profile: **40 participants from 19 countries**

- Researchers: 15
- European institutions (DG AGRI, DG CLIMA, JRC, Evaluation Helpdesk, EP): 3
- Public authorities / policy makers (local, regional, national): 1
- Advisors / innovation brokers / intermediaries: 4
- NGOs (local, regional, national, European): 8
- Other: 4
- EU-funded projects (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg, etc.): 3
- Civil society organisations (local, regional, national, European): 1
- Agri-food industry, business and rural entrepreneurs: 1

Figure 4. Second EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop by typology of stakeholders

In terms of areas of expertise, the profile of the participants showed a strong concentration in policy-related fields, especially the **CAP, rural development, and food systems**. This was complemented by significant expertise in **agriculture, climate, and environmental issues**. More limited, but still relevant, expertise was identified in **behavioural science, digitalisation, innovation**, and issues related to **economic sustainability and investment**.

Preparation and organisation: The second workshop was prepared as a policy hackathon aimed at moving beyond problem identification towards the co-design of solutions and policy recommendations. Building on the outcomes of the first workshop, participants were selected to ensure complementary expertise across policy, research, advisory services, innovation support and practical implementation. Particular attention was given to

creating a balanced mix of profiles capable of working collaboratively on future-oriented policy challenges related to the expansion of Climate-Smart Agriculture by 2030 and 2040. Preparatory work included the development of challenge statements, background materials and facilitated working methods designed to encourage structured discussion and solution-building among participants from different sectors and governance levels.

Challenges encountered: The main challenge was creating conditions for effective collaborative work among participants with diverse backgrounds and perspectives. Unlike the first workshop, which focused on validating findings, this session required participants to jointly develop policy solutions and recommendations. This demanded careful preparation of challenge statements that were ambitious enough to stimulate innovation while remaining grounded in policy realities. Additional challenges included balancing long-term strategic thinking with practical implementation considerations and ensuring that proposed solutions reflected both EU-level priorities and national and regional realities.

Speakers and contributions: The agenda combined BEATLES project updates with EU policy perspectives. **Serafín Pazos-Vidal** from AEIDL opened the session, while **Marilena Gemtou** from AUA presented the latest BEATLES project results. **Blanca Casares** from AEIDL presented findings on CAP support in the BEATLES Use Cases, focusing on policy barriers and opportunities for advancing CSA. **Ricard Ramon i Sumoy** from DG AGRI contributed with an overview of the EU policy landscape for agriculture, including the vision and preparation for the new CAP. These contributions provided the policy and evidence base for the subsequent hackathon exercise.

Materials:

- [Highlights report](#)
- [Presentations](#)
- [Recordings](#)
- [News item](#)

Results, policy learning and uptake: The workshop strengthened participants' understanding of the evolving EU agricultural policy landscape and helped translate BEATLES findings into more operational and future-oriented policy options linked to the transition towards CSA. The policy hackathon format encouraged participants to move beyond problem identification and engage collectively in the co-design of practical responses, implementation pathways and governance approaches for scaling up CSA towards 2030 and 2040.

Through the collaborative group work, participants exchanged experiences across policy, research, advisory and innovation contexts, helping to build capacities for systems thinking, solution-oriented policy design and multi-actor collaboration. The workshop also fostered mutual learning on how behavioural, economic, governance and social factors influence the uptake of CSA practices, while allowing participants to test the feasibility, coherence and transferability of different policy approaches across national and regional contexts.

In addition, the workshop generated concrete solution-oriented insights that could feed into the refinement of BEATLES policy recommendations, policy tools and the wider exploitation strategy. It also helped identify which policy narratives, governance mechanisms and implementation measures were considered most relevant and actionable by policy audiences.

3.3.3 Third EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop

The third EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop aimed to **further explore the concept of fairness in EU policy**, building on the work carried out so far in BEATLES and on an **expert consultation** conducted between November 2024 and April 2025. The discussion focused on how distributive, procedural, informational and interpersonal fairness could be considered in policy design, implementation and evaluation, and how fairness could support the uptake of CSA.

The workshop combined expert presentations, breakout discussions and plenary exchange. The expert inputs helped frame fairness as both a normative principle and a practical governance dimension affecting policy legitimacy, stakeholder participation, access to support, administrative complexity, value-chain relations and territorial inequalities.

Following these presentations, participants were divided into two breakout groups. The exercise asked them to turn fairness-related recommendations into actionable policy steps by identifying practical opportunities, relevant stakeholders and initial implementation measures. The breakout discussions focused on issues such as evidence-based and participatory evaluation, the assessment of winners and losers, context-specific policy design, inclusive consultations, links between fairness and sustainability, and the need to make policy trade-offs more explicit.

The workshop concluded with a plenary exchange where the two groups shared their main reflections and discussed how fairness could be made more operational in EU agricultural and food policy.

Date: 19 May 2025

Format: Online

Participants profile: 25 participants from 16 countries

- Researchers: 13
- European institutions (EC, EP, EESC, CoR, etc.): 3
- Public authorities / policy makers (local, regional, national): 1
- Advisors / innovation brokers / intermediaries: 1
- NGOs (local, regional, national, European): 3
- Other: 2
- EU-funded projects (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg, etc.): 1
- Civil society organisations (local, regional, national, European): 2

Figure 5. Third EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop by typology of stakeholders

In terms of areas of expertise, the 25 experts involved were mainly active in **agricultural and food policy** (24%), **food systems and sustainability** (21%), and the **Common Agricultural Policy** (18%). Additional expertise was identified in **economics and behavioural science** (15%), **legal and governance issues** (9%), **technology and innovation** (6%), and **gender and social issues** (6%).

Preparation and organisation: The preparation of the third workshop focused on exploring fairness as a cross-cutting dimension of Climate-Smart Agriculture and agri-food policy. Stakeholder selection prioritised experts with experience in agricultural policy, rural development, social inclusion, behavioural change, evaluation and governance. In addition to activating the existing Working Group network, targeted outreach was undertaken to engage specialists capable of contributing perspectives on distributive, procedural and recognition-related aspects of fairness. Preparatory work involved synthesising findings from the project's fairness assessment activities and developing discussion materials that could support reflection on how fairness considerations might be integrated into policy design, implementation and evaluation processes.

Challenges encountered: Fairness is a multidimensional (distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational) and often contested concept, making it challenging to frame discussions in a way that was both analytically robust and practically relevant for policy makers. A key difficulty was identifying experts capable of connecting theoretical and normative discussions on fairness with concrete agricultural and policy implementation contexts. Additional challenges included ensuring that different perspectives were represented, facilitating constructive dialogue around potentially sensitive issues, and translating broad fairness principles into actionable recommendations that could inform future policy development and implementation.

Speakers and contributions: The agenda brought together behavioural, economic, institutional and policy perspectives on fairness. **Jesús Barreiro-Hurle** from the Joint Research Centre presented the role of behavioural insights in agricultural policymaking. **Michiel van Galen** from Wageningen Research presented BEATLES work on fair value propositions and fair business models. **Florian Marian** from the European Economic and Social Committee discussed just transition in EU agri-food systems. **Blanca Casares** from AEIDL presented the concept of fairness within EU policies, including the findings of the

BEATLES expert consultation. These contributions helped connect the conceptual discussion on fairness with practical questions of governance, policy evaluation, stakeholder participation and CSA implementation.

Materials:

- [Highlights report](#)
- [Presentations](#)
- [Recordings](#)
- [News item](#)
- [Policy Brief](#) 'The notion of supply chain fairness in the EU policies related to Climate-Smart Agriculture' (background information)

Results, policy learning and uptake: The workshop helped participants deepen their understanding of fairness as a multidimensional principle in agricultural and food policy-making, while also translating expert knowledge and stakeholder reflections into more operational policy-oriented outputs.

It also strengthened participants' capacities to reflect on fairness not only as a social objective, but as a practical governance dimension affecting the legitimacy, effectiveness and long-term uptake of CSA policies and transitions. By introducing distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational fairness at the beginning of the session, the workshop provided a common framework for discussing access to support, administrative complexity, value-chain relations, participation in decision-making and territorial inequalities. The breakout exercise then allowed participants to move from conceptual reflection to implementation-oriented discussion, identifying practical opportunities, relevant stakeholders and initial policy steps to make fairness more operational in EU agricultural and food policy.

The outputs generated through the workshop, including stakeholder reflections, expert inputs and implementation-oriented ideas, can support the continued use and exploitation of BEATLES findings through policy briefs, consultation contributions, policy recommendations, and CSA policy tools. In addition, the workshop connected BEATLES work with ongoing EU policy debates and strategic processes, including the consultation on the future of EU farm policy, discussions surrounding the next Multiannual Financial Framework, and the Vision for Agriculture and Food.

3.3.4 Fourth EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop

The final Working Group workshop was organised as a policy session during the [BEATLES Final Event](#) to present and discuss the BEATLES policy recommendations and tools. It focused on how these outputs could be applied and scaled through current and upcoming EU policy instruments, particularly in the context of the post-2027 CAP and the 2028–2034 EU programming period.

The session marked the final step of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group process, moving from discussion and co-design towards policy uptake and exploitation. It combined the presentation of BEATLES policy outputs with an expert roundtable involving representatives of EU institutions and relevant organisations. This format provided an opportunity to reflect on the future relevance of BEATLES results and their potential contribution to ongoing debates on agricultural transition, behavioural insights, climate-smart policy design and future EU programming.

Date: 2 June 2026

Format: In-person

Participants profile: 100 participants¹ from 15 countries

- Researchers: 25
- European institutions (EC, EP, EESC, CoR, etc.): 13
- Public authorities / policy makers (local, regional, national): 7
- Advisors / innovation brokers / intermediaries: 6
- NGOs (local, regional, national, European): 10
- Other: 10
- EU-funded projects (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg, etc.): 10
- Civil society organisations (local, regional, national, European): 9
- Farmers, producer & producers associations: 5
- Agri-food industry, business and rural entrepreneurs: 5

Preparation and organisation: Preparation for the final conference combined logistical planning, stakeholder engagement and content development. Activities included securing the venue, developing the agenda, confirming speakers, preparing communication materials, promoting the event and managing the registration process. Particular attention was devoted to the preparation of the BEATLES policy results dossier and supporting materials, which synthesised the project's main findings, policy recommendations and tools in an accessible format for policy-makers and other stakeholders.

Given the in-person format, participation was managed through an expression of interest process. Registrations were reviewed and confirmed according to participant profiles, ensuring a balanced representation of policy-makers, researchers, advisory organisations, EU institutions, networks and other relevant stakeholders. Particular attention was given to Brussels-based organisations and stakeholders working on agriculture, the CAP and Climate-Smart Agriculture, while Permanent Representations, Members of the European

¹ The signed attendance list includes 80 confirmed participants. However, additional attendees took part in the Final Conference but did not sign the attendance sheet. Therefore, total attendance is estimated at around 100 participants.

Parliament, AGRI Committee representatives and regional offices were also specifically targeted through personalised outreach.

The final policy session was designed to present and discuss the main policy recommendations and tools developed throughout the BEATLES project and to explore their potential uptake within current and future EU policy frameworks. Preparation focused on bringing together participants with the capacity to influence policy debates and implementation processes, while ensuring a diversity of institutional perspectives and expertise. Particular attention was devoted to translating project outputs into a dossier of results and concise and actionable policy messages and demonstrating their practical relevance for ongoing discussions on CAP implementation, simplification efforts and the post-2027 policy framework.

Challenges encountered: The main challenge was designing a programme that effectively balanced two complementary objectives: presenting the project's overall results and achievements, while also creating sufficient space for a focused policy discussion on the uptake and future application of the BEATLES policy recommendations and tools. This required careful coordination of content and speakers to ensure that both dimensions remained relevant and engaging for participants with different interests and professional backgrounds.

A further challenge was ensuring a balanced representation of stakeholder groups, including EU institutions, national and regional authorities, advisory organisations, research actors, networks and practitioners. Particular efforts were devoted to engaging high-level policy stakeholders and institutional representatives whose perspectives were especially relevant to discussions on CAP implementation and future policy frameworks. Securing their participation required early planning, targeted outreach and continuous follow-up, given the constraints imposed by institutional agendas and competing policy commitments. Maintaining a diversity of perspectives while ensuring meaningful policy-oriented discussions was therefore a key consideration throughout the preparation process.

Speakers and contributions: The opening session introduced the BEATLES project journey and included a keynote address from **Ricard Ramon i Sumoy** from DG AGRI on the role of the CAP and future policy instruments in supporting sustainable change. This was followed by an intervention from **Serafín Pazos-Vidal** from AEIDL on opportunities within the 2028–2034 MFF to scale behavioural approaches in sustainable food systems.

The policy session was moderated by **Spyros Fountas** from the Agricultural University of Athens and opened with the presentation of the BEATLES policy recommendations and CSA Policy Toolkit by **Blanca Casares Guillén** from AEIDL. This presentation introduced the main policy-oriented outputs developed under WP5 and framed their relevance for future agricultural, climate and food-system policy discussions.

The session continued with an expert roundtable on how BEATLES recommendations and tools could be applied and scaled through current and upcoming EU policy instruments. The roundtable brought together **María Fuentes Merino** from DG AGRI, **Emanuele Ciriolo** from the Joint Research Centre, **Stoyan Tchoukanov** from the European Economic and Social Committee, and **Krystyna Springer** from the Institute for European Environmental Policy. Together, they explored how the project's recommendations could be translated into real-world action, including through the integration of behavioural insights into the CAP, the use of performance-based approaches and coordinated support for farmers adopting climate-smart practices.

Materials:

- News item
 - [BEATLES](#)
 - [AEIDL](#)
 - [EU CAP Network](#)
- [Results brochure](#) (background document)

Results, policy learning and uptake: The final policy session connected the Working Group process more directly with exploitation and future policy uptake. It provided an opportunity to present the project's policy recommendations and CSA Policy Toolkit to EU-level stakeholders and to discuss how these outputs could inform ongoing and upcoming EU policy discussions, including the post-2027 CAP and the 2028–2034 programming period.

The session helped position BEATLES results within wider debates on agricultural transition, behavioural insights, climate-smart policy design and future EU programming. It also supported the identification of potential uptake pathways for the recommendations and tools, particularly among policymakers, advisory actors and organisations involved in CAP-related implementation and policy support.

By bringing the Working Group process together with the Final Event, the session helped close the loop between project research, stakeholder dialogue and policy-oriented exploitation. In this way, it contributed to strengthening the visibility, relevance and potential future use of BEATLES policy outputs beyond the lifetime of the project.

3.4 Complementary activities for capacity building

In addition to the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops and final policy session, WP5 carried out complementary policy-support activities that helped bring BEATLES findings closer to policy audiences. These activities included contributions to EU consultations, policy briefs, exchanges with other BEATLES work packages and collaboration with relevant EU initiatives.

3.4.1 Contributions to EU consultations

Beyond the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops, BEATLES also contributed to a range of European policy consultations, institutional reflection processes and stakeholder dialogues linked to Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA), sustainable food systems and the future of EU agricultural policy. These activities complemented the project's capacity-building and policy-learning objectives by connecting BEATLES findings to ongoing policy debates and providing opportunities to test and position project recommendations within real policy processes.

Between 2022 and 2026, BEATLES contributed to several consultation and policy-feedback exercises involving the European Commission, the European Committee of the Regions, expert dialogue processes and other institutional initiatives. These contributions addressed topics including sustainable food systems, CAP reform and implementation, climate adaptation and mitigation, resilience of agri-food systems, simplification of EU funding instruments, fairness in food supply chains and the future governance architecture of EU agriculture and rural development.

The contributions drew on evidence generated across the BEATLES project, including behavioural research, sustainability assessments, use case analysis, policy mapping activities and discussions developed through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group. In particular, the consultations provided opportunities to bring forward project reflections regarding behavioural barriers and enabling conditions for CSA uptake, governance and

implementation challenges within the CAP, fairness considerations in agri-food transitions, and the need for more integrated, territorially adapted and operational policy frameworks.

These activities also contributed to the refinement and validation of the policy recommendations and tools developed under Deliverable 5.1. At the same time, they strengthened the exploitation and policy uptake potential of BEATLES outputs by increasing their visibility among EU policy actors and positioning project findings within ongoing discussions on the future of EU agri-food policy, including debates related to the post-2027 CAP framework and future National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs).

Figure 6 provides a visual overview of BEATLES' contributions to EU consultations and policy processes between 2022 and 2026. Overall, **25 contributions** were made by the project, led by AEIDL and validated by the BEATLES consortium. These contributions can be grouped into four main areas:

- Common Agricultural Policy and agri-food systems.
- Environmental and climate policy.
- EU budget and competitiveness.
- Heritage, intergenerational fairness and rural future.

Figure 6. Feedback to EU consultations and policy processes

Taken together, these activities show that BEATLES' capacity-building efforts went beyond workshop-based exchange. They also included direct engagement with evolving EU policy processes, strengthening the visibility, relevance and future uptake of WP5 outputs.

3.4.2 Policy briefs

As part of its wider policy-support and capacity-building work under WP5, BEATLES produced **four policy briefs** to translate project evidence into concise, accessible and policy-relevant messages. These briefs were designed for policy makers, policy advisors and other stakeholders involved in agricultural, food, climate and rural policy.

The policy briefs addressed four complementary themes: [the future CAP reform](#), [fairness in food supply chains](#), [barriers and drivers in EU policies for Climate-Smart Agriculture](#), and [multi-level governance for the post-2027 policy framework](#). They were used to frame

discussions within WP5, support the preparation of EU Multi-Actor Working Group activities, inform consultation inputs, and contribute to the wider exploitation of BEATLES findings through more accessible and targeted communication formats.

By 23 June 2026, the four policy briefs, hosted in the [Publications section](#) of the AEIDL website, had recorded **319 downloads**. The related **news articles** published on the AEIDL website had also reached **968 views**:

- [The road to the post 2027 Common Agricultural Policy](#) (Oct 3, 2023)
- [AEIDL analyses the notion of supply chain fairness in the EU policies related to Climate-Smart Agriculture](#) (May 13, 2024)
- [Barriers and drivers across EU policies to achieve Climate-Smart Agriculture](#) (Nov 13, 2024)
- [Multi-level governance at the breaking point: are Member States prepared for the post 2027 Common Agricultural Policy?](#) (Nov 4, 2025)

Figure 7. BEATLES policy briefs and outreach figures

The Road to the Post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy

(September 2023)

118 downloads
483 article views

Ensuring Fairness in Agricultural and Food Supply Chains

(May 2024)

52 downloads
129 article views

Barriers and Drivers in EU Policies for Climate-Smart Agriculture

(November 2024)

64 downloads
117 article views

Multi-level Governance at the Breaking Point: Are Member States Prepared for the New CAP Integration?

(October 2025)

85 downloads
239 article views

Together, they provided concise entry points for policy audiences and helped increase the visibility and uptake of WP5 results in discussions on CAP reform, fairness, policy coherence and governance for Climate-Smart Agriculture.

The full policy content of these briefs is presented in D5.1, *Policy recommendations and tools*.

3.4.3 Contributions to and from other BEATLES Work Packages

The capacity-building and policy-support activities reported in D5.3 were closely interconnected with the work carried out across the different BEATLES work packages.

These interactions were essential because the policy recommendations, policy tools and mutual-learning activities developed under WP5 were not produced in isolation. Instead, they were continuously informed by behavioural research, sustainability assessments, co-creation activities, business-model analysis, advisory-system work and dissemination activities developed throughout the project. In turn, WP5 contributed to increasing the policy relevance, visibility and exploitation potential of outputs generated in other work packages.

First, WP5 drew on the **co-creation work carried out with the BEATLES use cases**. A first important contribution came from the co-creation activities and Living Lab processes implemented through WP1 and the BEATLES Use Cases. WP1 established the methodological and participatory foundations of the project through stakeholder mapping, systematic reviews, surveys, interviews and co-creation workshops involving multi-stakeholder identification and engagement across the agri-food value chain. Before the implementation of the first round of Co-Creation Workshops, specific preparatory and capacity-building activities were organised for the Use Case leaders. These activities aimed to ensure a shared understanding of the methodological and policy objectives of the workshops, as well as a coherent implementation approach across the different territories and value chains.

These workshops generated important evidence on the “lock-ins” and “levers” affecting Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) transitions. Stakeholders identified barriers linked to fragmented policy frameworks, insufficient advisory support, lack of strategic financing, weak stakeholder coordination, low consumer awareness and limited implementation of CSA objectives within the CAP. At the same time, they identified enabling conditions such as growing climate awareness, digitalisation opportunities, stricter environmental regulation and the potential role of CAP reform as a driver of systemic transition.

WP5 used these findings extensively to contextualise the discussions held within the EU Multi-Actor Working Group and to ensure that the BEATLES policy recommendations reflected practical implementation realities observed in the five Use Cases. The interaction with WP1 therefore helped connect EU-level policy reflections with territorial experiences and sector-specific implementation challenges. In particular, evidence generated through the co-creation workshops informed discussions on CAP implementation, governance complexity, advisory-system needs, fairness, regional adaptation of policy instruments and the importance of place-based approaches for CSA transitions.

Second, WP5 contributed to **internal capacity building** by supporting use case partners and project teams in reflecting on policy needs and policy relevance. This included exchanges with use case leaders and the synthesis of policy-related insights emerging from the first two years of project implementation. These activities helped connect local and sectoral experiences with broader EU-level policy discussions and ensured that policy recommendations were grounded in the realities of the BEATLES use cases.

Third, the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops created links with other technical and analytical strands of the project. For example, the **portfolio of fair value propositions** developed in WP4 by Wageningen University & Research was presented during the third EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop. This contribution helped connect conceptual discussions on fairness with operational questions related to governance, market incentives, value distribution and behavioural change. More broadly, the interaction with WP4 was also relevant, as work on **business models and value propositions** provided important insights into the economic and organisational conditions influencing CSA uptake. These inputs helped WP5 reflect on how policy frameworks can support viable business models, reduce adoption barriers and create enabling conditions for farmers and

other agri-food actors. WP5, therefore, acted as a bridge translating the analytical work carried out under WP4 into more operational policy reflections and recommendations.

Figure 8. Presentation of fair CSA value propositions developed by WP3 during the third EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop

The image shows a presentation slide from a video conference. The slide is titled "Fair CSA value propositions: conclusions" and lists several key findings. A video inset on the right shows a man wearing headphones speaking. The slide footer includes the date "19/05/2025" and the text "BEATLES | 3rd EU Multi-actor working group, Online".

- "Climate-smart" was not (yet) used in value propositions for food in supermarkets
- Many value propositions
 - Focus on easy communication; good for nature, good for people, good for workers
 - Certification labels: Fair trade, Rainforest Alliance, Organic
 - Do not specify CSA practices like precision agriculture, or soil management
- Local, collective (farmers – local government) business models misalign with large supermarket chains
- Premiums to farmers for specific practices are rarely mentioned
- Transparency (other than part of tracking and tracing) is rarely used
- Some value proposition show farmers, but rarely used in combination with explanation of CSA practices and costs/benefits
- Some value seems difficult to sell to consumers > role for government but it would be good to include that in the value proposition as well, or "Funded by the EU"

In addition, feedback collected from stakeholders on the usability of BEATLES tools and results **informed the Theory of Change work developed under WP3**, particularly in relation to the project's KPI and targets for the participation in the workshop and learning of participants.

Regarding the **Advisors' Guide developed under Task 5.3** within the same work package, WP5 contributed through a continuous working relationship established with the task leader, Naturland, including regular coordination exchanges and biannual meetings throughout the project duration. AEIDL also contributed directly to the content of the Advisors' Guide by supporting the development of a dedicated section focusing on policy instruments, policy recommendations and the role of advisors from an "advisor-for-advisors" perspective. This contribution aimed to strengthen the connection between Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) advisory practices and the broader EU policy and governance framework, particularly in relation to the CAP, sustainability objectives and future transition pathways.

The section developed under WP5 provides advisors with a more policy-oriented perspective on CSA implementation, including explanations of relevant policy instruments, governance mechanisms, enabling conditions and practical recommendations that can support advisory services when accompanying farmers and other agri-food actors in climate transitions. This contribution will form part of **Deliverable D5.2 Support guide and training for Advisors**.

Strong **interactions also developed with WP6 on dissemination, communication and exploitation**. Throughout the project, additional dissemination and policy communication activities were also developed to increase the visibility, accessibility and practical relevance of BEATLES policy work. These activities included the preparation of dissemination articles and news items published through the project and AEIDL websites, focusing on ongoing EU legislative and policy processes related to Climate-Smart Agriculture, the CAP reform debate, food-system sustainability, fairness and rural governance.

In this context, AEIDL prepared the article [*"Shaping the transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture through multi-actor policy dialogue"*](#) published on the EU CAP Network website on 9 July 2025, to highlight the policy dialogue and capacity-building activities

carried out under WP5. In addition, AEIDL contributed to the article [“Supporting the transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture with the EU-funded BEATLES project”](#), published on the EU CAP Network website on 18 June 2026, which presented the project's policy-oriented outcomes, including the BEATLES policy recommendations, the CSA Policy Toolkit, EU consultation contributions and related capacity-building resources.

In addition, the feedback and contributions submitted by the project to EU public consultations and policy processes were often translated into more accessible and dissemination-oriented communication materials. This helped communicate BEATLES policy reflections and recommendations to broader audiences beyond institutional stakeholders, including advisory organisations, researchers, networks and civil society actors.

The project also ensured active participation in key European events, conferences, policy dialogues and stakeholder exchanges related to agriculture, climate transition, rural development and food systems. These activities contributed to strengthening the visibility of BEATLES results, positioning the project within ongoing European policy debates and facilitating exchanges with other Horizon Europe projects, EU institutions, CAP networks and relevant agri-food stakeholders.

A further example of cross-work package collaboration was the webinar [“Turning CAP Policy into CSA Action”](#), organised by WP6 on 17 March 2026. The event brought together policymakers, researchers, practitioners, civil society representatives, farmers and other agri-food stakeholders to discuss how forthcoming EU policy and funding reforms could better support Climate-Smart Agriculture. AEIDL contributed insights from WP5 on policy recommendations, including the implications of the upcoming Multiannual Financial Framework 2028–2034, findings related to CAP Strategic Plans, and opportunities to strengthen performance and data frameworks for improved CSA outcomes.

Figure 9. Presentation of the BEATLES CSA policy tools during the “Turning CAP Policy into CSA Action” webinar

BEATLES

BEATLES policy tools

Tool 1 — CSA Policy Readiness & Enabling Conditions Checklist

- Diagnostic tool assessing institutional, financial and governance conditions
- Identifies policy gaps and enabling actions
- Supports development of CSA roadmaps

Tool 2 — CSA Intervention design Tool for NRPP (2028–2034)

- Translates practice-level evidence into policy interventions
- Uses analysis of 25 CSA practices across 5 EU Member States
- Supports CAP-related and non-CAP related intervention design and implementation

Tool 3 — CSA Performance Monitoring Tool for NRPP (2028–2034)

- Defines CSA performance indicators
- Supports monitoring and evaluation of CSA outcomes
- Links interventions to productivity, resilience and mitigation impacts

policy readiness → intervention design → performance monitoring

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3.4.4 Synergies and collaboration with EU initiatives

BEATLES established synergies with relevant Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, EU networks and related initiatives to promote collaboration, facilitate knowledge exchange and increase the visibility of project results beyond the consortium. These collaborations included participation in external events, dissemination of BEATLES materials through other projects' channels, invitations to BEATLES events, co-organisation of joint activities, exchange of news items, and the inclusion of sister projects' logos and website links on the BEATLES website. More detailed information on these synergies is provided in D6.4 *Dissemination and Communication Plan*.

Overall, BEATLES identified and **engaged with over 40 projects and initiatives**, mainly focused on sustainable agriculture, climate-smart farming, food systems transformation, agroecology, digitalisation, rural innovation, policy support and advisory services. These included the two sister projects funded under the same call, VISIONARY and ENFASYS, as well as other relevant initiatives such as PRUDENT, CODECS, Climate Farm Demo, D4AgEcol, EU CAP Network, FOOD 2030 project collaboration Network, ECO-READY, REENFORCE, GOOD, ICAERUS, ModernAKIS, CLEVERFOOD, FOODPathS, FUTURAL, SMART ERA, RURACTIVE, B-TRUST and thERBN. In addition, **over 30 joint actions** were implemented with sister projects, EU initiatives and relevant networks.

These synergies are relevant for D5.3 because they created additional routes for the dissemination, validation and future use of WP5 policy-oriented outputs. Some projects and initiatives can also be considered potential early adopters, end users or multipliers of BEATLES results. Projects working on multi-actor engagement and behavioural change can reuse elements of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group approach; advisory, AKIS and farm-support initiatives can benefit from BEATLES insights on barriers, enabling conditions and advisory needs; and policy-oriented projects and networks can use or disseminate BEATLES policy recommendations and the CSA Policy Toolkit.

Table 2 summarises the main synergies and collaboration activities most relevant for policy makers and policy advisors. These activities helped create additional pathways for the future uptake of BEATLES outputs by connecting WP5 policy messages with projects and networks able to reuse, adapt or promote them beyond the project lifetime.

Table 2. Main synergies and collaboration activities

Activity / Initiative	Type of collaboration	Added value
ELIF EU policy webinar with FUTURAL, SMART ERA and RURACTIVE	Policy webinar organised by AEIDL on 25 November 2024.	Created a policy-oriented space to explore smart development in EU rural policies, the mainstreaming of sustainability practices, and the role of communities in rural development and local action.
“Turning CAP Policy into CSA Action” BEATLES webinar with PRUDENT	BEATLES WP5 participation in the WP6 webinar on 17 March 2026.	Connected BEATLES policy recommendations and CSA tools with future EU policy and funding reforms, including the MFF 2028–2034. PRUDENT provided a complementary perspective through its Toolbox.
ECO-READY policy workshop	BEATLES participation in the ECO-READY workshop “Delivering impact: building the ECO-READY legacy for food systems”.	Supported exchange on food-system resilience, policy uptake and long-term impact pathways.
Final BEATLES event / fourth EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop	Participation of ENFASYS, VISIONARY, PRUDENT, B-TRUST and thERBN as commentators.	Provided external feedback on BEATLES results and connected WP5 policy outputs with projects working on sustainable agriculture, behavioural change, trust, innovation and circular bioeconomy.

Rural Pact Support Office

Promotion of EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops.

Helped increase the reach of the Working Group among rural development actors, policy stakeholders and organisations interested in CSA.

EU CAP Network

Promotion of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops.

Helped connect BEATLES policy messages with CAP-related audiences, including policy makers, advisory actors, rural networks and stakeholders involved in sustainable agri-food value chains.

Publication of the articles [“Shaping the transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture through multi-actor policy dialogue”](#), and [“Supporting the transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture with the EU-funded BEATLES project”](#).

Participation in the Forum on Best Practices in the Agri-Food Supply Chain.

3.5 Contribution to project KPIs

Monitoring and evaluation were an important part of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group process. They helped assess whether the workshops and related policy-support activities were relevant, useful and aligned with the objectives of Task 5.4, *Mutual learning and capacity building for policy action*.

The indicators used for D5.3 focused on three main dimensions:

- Delivery of the planned capacity-building workshops.
- Participation of policy makers and policy-relevant actors.
- Evidence that participants felt better informed about BEATLES results and their relevance for policy design and implementation.

For the purpose of this section, “policy makers and policy-relevant actors” include representatives of EU institutions, national and regional public authorities, Managing Authorities, CAP-related bodies, policy advisors and invited policy experts directly involved in policy design, implementation, monitoring, evaluation or policy support.

Table 3. EU Multi-Actor Working Group monitoring indicators

BEATLES result	Proposed indicator	Reference value	Reached target (M48)
			4 workshops
	Number of EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops organised and delivered	3 workshops	Evidence: 3 workshops delivered + 1 policy session
Mutual learning and capacity-building workshops presenting BEATLES policy options			57 policy makers
	Number of policy makers participating across the three workshops	> 20	Evidence: 47 policy makers and policy-relevant actors participated in workshops + final policy session
			10 policy makers participated in consultations

	Share of participating policy makers reporting that they feel better informed	≥50%	97% of respondents reported feeling better informed (from 35 responses received in forms after workshops online)
Policy makers better informed about project results to design and implement policies	Total number of policy makers and policy-relevant actors informed through D5.3-related activities	50	>300 policy-relevant actors informed Evidence: 220 participants engaged through workshops and the final conference. 9 UC leaders and national experts interviewed during the policy consultation process. 8 national responses received through the CAP Use Cases consultation. 12 experts provided detailed feedback through the fairness assessment consultation. Additional dissemination reached policy-relevant stakeholders through online communication activities
	National rural or CAP networks informed	>20	28 CAP/rural national networks informed
	EU institution representatives informed	>10	90 institutional representatives informed through workshop materials and related dissemination
	Key actionable policy recommendations produced	5	12 at EU level + 5 at Use Case level + 3 Tools
Policy recommendations produced	Outputs used by relevant policy networks (CAP network, EIP-AGRI, etc.)	2	2 used by the EU CAP Network
	BEATLES consortia advise relevant EU, national or regional policy processes	1	25

The EU Multi-Actor Working Group achieved the core capacity-building targets linked to Task 5.4. The four planned workshops were organised and delivered, and the target of **more than 20 policy makers participating in mutual learning workshops was also exceeded**, with 47 policy makers and policy-relevant actors participating across the workshop series. In addition, 10 policy makers participated in consultation activities, bringing the total number of policy makers engaged through D5.3-related activities to 57.

It should also be noted that the reach of D5.3-related activities went beyond the direct participants involved in the workshops. Wider outreach was achieved through the dissemination of results, the sharing of information with national CAP Networks, follow-up communication with invited stakeholders who could not attend the events, and the use of other multiplier organisations and relevant EU-level networks. These channels helped increase the visibility and reach of BEATLES policy messages and capacity-building results among policy makers, advisory actors, rural development stakeholders and other organisations interested in Climate-Smart Agriculture.

Post-event feedback also suggests that the workshops contributed positively to policy learning. Across the first three online EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops, **35 feedback responses were received**: 15 from the first workshop, 14 from the second

workshop and 6 from the third workshop. Among respondents, **97% reported feeling better informed** after participating in the workshops.

In addition to the project-level targets, **supplementary indicators** were used to assess participants' perceptions of the **quality, usefulness and practical relevance** of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops. These indicators were designed to complement participation data by capturing how respondents assessed the content provided, the quality of exchanges and the usability of the project outputs. They included:

- The share of participants rating the quality of content and presentations above "good".
- The share of participants rating the quality of discussions, exchanges and participation above "good".
- The share of participants considering the project results, findings, recommendations and tools useful and implementable.

Whether participants reported identifying policy aspects or considerations they had not previously taken into account. Responses highlighted issues such as how policies are shaped and influenced, the role of political factors in enabling or limiting transition processes, North–South biases in research and interventions, links between CSA and CAP-supported practices, and farmer typologies. Overall, the KPI evidence indicates that the EU Multi-Actor Working Group contributed to the delivery of BEATLES capacity-building objectives. It reached the expected number of workshops, exceeded the minimum target for policy maker participation, exceeded the wider target for informing policy-relevant actors, and generated positive feedback on participants' perceived learning.

4. Exploitation and sustainability plan

4.1 Purpose and alignment with the BEATLES Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

This section provides a concise summary of how the policy-oriented outputs supported through WP5 can remain visible, accessible and reusable beyond the lifetime of the BEATLES project. It focuses on the outputs connected to the EU Multi-Actor Working Group and related capacity-building activities, including the BEATLES policy recommendations, the CSA Policy Toolkit, policy briefs, consultation inputs, workshop materials and final policy session outputs.

The section is aligned with the project-level *BEATLES Exploitation and Sustainability Plan* developed under WP6. D5.3 does not introduce new Key Exploitable Results, as these are already defined at project level. Instead, it explains how the activities reported in this deliverable contribute to the existing KERs most closely linked to WP5 policy and capacity-building work:

- **KER6 - Policy recommendations and tools.**
- **KER3 - Methodology and implementation of co-creation activities within BEATLES.**
- **KER5 - Farm Advice Guide and related advisory outcomes.**

Given the scope of D5.3, this section is not intended to replace the project-level exploitation plan. Its purpose is to show, in a proportionate way, how the capacity-building process helped validate, disseminate and position WP5 policy outputs for future use by policy

makers, policy advisors, advisory actors, CAP/rural networks and other stakeholders involved in CSA transitions.

4.2 Contribution to project-level KERs

The table below summarises how D5.3 contributes to the relevant project-level KERs, identifying the main WP5 contribution, target users, exploitation route and sustainability mechanism.

Table 4. Simplified exploitation roadmap for D5.3 contributions to project-level KERs

KER	Main WP5 contribution	Target users	Exploitation route	Sustainability mechanism
KER6 - Policy recommendations and tools: CSA Tool Suite	D5.1 on Policy recommendations and tools, online policy toolkit, policy briefs, consultation inputs and related policy-support materials.	Policy makers and policy advisors at EU, national and regional levels; EU institutions; Managing Authorities; ministries; CAP Strategic Plan teams; Paying Agencies; advisory bodies; CAP/rural networks; researchers and policy-support organisations. Additional users include organisations supporting agricultural transition, policy innovation and future capacity-building activities through ELIF and other EU networks.	Direct policy and societal exploitation through use in policy diagnosis, design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Outputs can support CAP-related discussions, consultation responses, policy briefings, training activities and future EU-funded projects.	Continued access through the BEATLES website, the CSA Tool Suite hosted on www.climatesmartagri.eu , AEIDL channels, Zenodo and relevant policy networks. AEIDL will maintain the toolkit online for seven years, supporting post-project visibility and reuse.
KER3 - Methodology and implementation of co-creation activities within BEATLES	D5.3 documents the EU Multi-Actor Working Group as a structured Science-Society-Policy space where BEATLES findings were discussed, tested and assessed by external experts and policy practitioners.	Research community and academia; policy makers and policy advisors; food system value-chain stakeholders, including farmers, advisors, industry actors, investors and consumers; EU-funded projects; Managing Authorities; and CAP/rural networks.	Reuse of the Working Group methodology, workshop formats, policy hackathon approach, expert roundtables and feedback mechanisms in future capacity-building, co-creation and policy-learning processes.	Dissemination of methodological lessons, workshop materials and practical formats through project and partner channels, including AEIDL's European Local Innovation Forum (ELIF) and future EU-funded initiatives.
KER5 - Farm Advice Guide: fair value propositions, business models portfolio and other main outcomes	D5.1 on Policy recommendations and tools supports the circulation of policy-relevant insights that can complement advisory materials (D5.2) and help connect farm-level change with wider policy, governance and support	Farmers, farm advisors, business advisors, agri-food industry actors, cooperatives, SMEs, corporates, farm-support organisations, advisory services, CAP/rural networks and organisations supporting	Knowledge-transfer and advisory exploitation through the use of BEATLES insights in advisory services, training activities, policy-oriented meetings and farm-support initiatives.	Continued dissemination through advisory networks, CAP/rural networks, partner channels and future training or capacity-building activities targeting advisors and farm-support organisations.

conditions for CSA uptake. agricultural transition.

This legacy is primarily reflected in the policy-oriented outputs developed under Deliverable D5.1 *Policy Recommendations and Tools*, both in its report version and in the web-based CSA Tool Suite environment (www.climatesmartagri.eu).

Figure 10. Climate-Smart Agricultural Toolkit

Overall, the contribution generated through WP5 extends beyond the production of individual policy outputs. **It represents the creation of a structured policy-learning and capacity-building framework capable of supporting future experimentation, institutional learning, implementation adaptation and policy uptake linked to Climate-Smart Agriculture transitions under evolving EU policy frameworks, including the post-2027 CAP and future National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs).**

4.3 From Policy Outputs to Capacity-Building Impact

The sustainability strategy for the EU Multi-Actor Working Group aims to ensure that the policy-oriented outputs generated under WP5 continue to be accessible, visible and useful beyond the lifetime of the BEATLES project. This approach is aligned with the project-level Exploitation and Sustainability Plan developed under WP6 and supports the continued uptake of the project-level KERs to which D5.3 contributes, particularly KER6 — Policy recommendations and tools, as well as the related contributions to KER3 and KER5.

The long-term value of these outputs lies in their capacity to support policy makers, policy advisors, Managing Authorities, CAP networks, advisory actors and other stakeholders involved in the transition towards Climate-Smart Agriculture. Rather than creating a new structure after the project, the sustainability approach focuses on embedding BEATLES

outputs in existing dissemination channels, policy-support networks, training activities, and future project opportunities.

The sustainability approach builds on three pillars:

1. Open access to tools and results.
2. Strategic dissemination and continued outreach.
3. Alignment with EU policy frameworks and future research and innovation initiatives.

4.3.1 Repository and open access to WP5 resources

To ensure the long-term availability, visibility and reuse of results, the main WP5 outputs linked to the EU Multi-Actor Working Group will remain accessible through project, partner and open-access platforms. These channels will help ensure that BEATLES policy outputs can continue to be consulted and reused by policy makers, policy advisors, researchers, advisory actors, rural networks and other stakeholders after the end of the project.

- **The BEATLES project website and document repository**, providing access to public deliverables, news items, policy outputs, workshop materials and other project resources: <https://beatles-project.eu/>
- **The CSA policy toolkit demonstrator prototype**, which will provide a structured entry point to WP5 policy recommendations, tools and supporting resources. The dashboard will be embedded into the project website before the end of the project and will remain available for seven years under AEIDL management.
- **EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops materials**, including highlights reports, presentations, recordings of plenary sessions and related news items. These materials will support continued learning and reuse in future policy discussions, training sessions and stakeholder engagement activities.
 - 1st EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop: [Presentations](#), [YouTube playlist](#).
 - 2nd EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop: [Presentations](#), [YouTube playlist](#).
 - 3rd EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshop: [Presentations](#), [YouTube playlist](#).
 - 4rd EU Multi-Actor Working Group at the Final event: [Dossier of results](#).
- **Zenodo**: all project outputs produced by AEIDL are uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring DOI-referenced open access: https://zenodo.org/communities/beatles_projecteu/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
- **The Horizon Results Platform**: relevant BEATLES Key Exploitable Results may be uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform to increase visibility among policy actors, potential adopters, researchers and future project consortia beyond the BEATLES consortium.
- **EU-FarmBook**: where relevant, BEATLES practice-oriented outputs may also be shared through EU-FarmBook to support wider dissemination among agricultural knowledge and innovation actors, advisors, researchers and practitioners.

Public outputs will be made available under a Creative Commons licence (CC-BY), where applicable, in line with the project-level IPR strategy. This will support ethical reuse by policy makers, researchers, civil society organisations and other stakeholders, while ensuring proper attribution to the BEATLES project and the relevant authors or partners.

4.3.2 Strategic dissemination and outreach for impact

Ensuring the long-term visibility and policy relevance of BEATLES WP5 outputs requires continued dissemination beyond the formal end of the project. Dissemination and outreach activities are therefore designed not only to publicise results, but also to position BEATLES as a useful source of evidence, recommendations and tools for policy actors working on Climate-Smart Agriculture, CAP implementation and agri-food transitions.

The dissemination approach will build on the activities already carried out through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group workshops, policy briefs, consultation inputs, stakeholder engagement processes, and contributions to and from other BEATLES Work Packages described in Section 3 of this deliverable. It will maintain momentum through coordinated actions by AEIDL and, where relevant, other project partners.

These actions may include:

- **Targeted sharing of BEATLES policy recommendations and toolkit materials** with EU institutions, Managing Authorities, CAP Strategic Plan teams, advisory bodies, CAP/rural networks and policy advisors.
- **Presentation of WP5 results at European, national and regional policy events** linked to the CAP, Climate-Smart Agriculture, sustainable food systems, biodiversity, climate action and rural development.
- **Publication and dissemination of policy-oriented materials**, including policy briefs, news items, articles, blogs, presentations and social media content.
- **Reuse of EU Multi-Actor Working Group materials** in future capacity-building activities, webinars, stakeholder workshops and policy learning exchanges.
- **Continued dissemination through AEIDL and partner networks**, including ELIF and other relevant European policy and rural development platforms.
- **Integration of BEATLES findings** into future EU-funded projects, consultation responses, policy-support activities and collaborative initiatives.

These actions will help sustain awareness and uptake of the BEATLES project-level KERs to which D5.3 contributes. In particular, they will support the continued use of the policy recommendations and CSA policy toolkit as practical resources for policy diagnosis, design, and monitoring.

4.3.3 Coordination with research and policy initiatives

To maximise long-term impact, BEATLES WP5 outputs will remain aligned with ongoing European policy processes and research and innovation initiatives. This is particularly important because the transition towards Climate-Smart Agriculture is closely linked to evolving debates on the post-2027 CAP, policy simplification, fairness in agri-food value chains, sustainability monitoring, advisory systems and future EU funding priorities.

The outputs developed through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group can continue contributing to:

- **European Parliament AGRI committee**, by sharing policy evidence and recommendations on emerging findings coming from the MAPs that informed a series of possible improvements of the draft CAP regulation and MFF 2028-2034.
- **CAP and rural networks**, which can act as multipliers for disseminating BEATLES recommendations, policy briefs and toolkit materials.
- **Future Horizon Europe, LIFE or Interreg initiatives**, where BEATLES tools, recommendations and policy insights can be reused, adapted or further developed.

- **Policy consultation processes**, where BEATLES findings can continue to inform responses to EU, national or regional consultations related to agriculture, food systems, climate, environment and rural development.
- **Future capacity-building and mutual learning activities** for policy actors, including through the ELIF.

5. Risk analysis, mitigation and contingency measures

The exploitation of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group outputs, including WP5's, involves several potential risks that could affect their long-term uptake, visibility and sustainability after the end of the BEATLES project. This analysis is aligned with the project-level exploitation framework in D6.7 and focuses on the KERs to which D5.3 contributes: KER3 — Methodology and implementation of co-creation activities, KER5 — Farm Advice Guide, and especially KER6 — Policy recommendations and tools.

The main risks relate to policy uptake, stakeholder engagement, long-term access, resource availability and the capacity of external actors to use BEATLES results in practice. Particular attention is given to the recommendations and CSA Policy Toolkit, the reuse of EU Multi-Actor Working Group materials, and the dissemination of policy-relevant insights through advisory and EU networks.

Table 5. Summary of key risks, mitigation and contingency measures

Risk	Description	Mitigation measure	Contingency measure
Limited uptake of policy recommendations and tools (KER6)	KER6 outputs may not be used by policy actors if they are not sufficiently connected to ongoing policy processes or if CSA is not prioritised in future policy agendas.	Target policy actors already engaged through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group, including EU institutions, Managing Authorities, CAP Strategic Plan teams, advisory bodies and CAP/rural networks.	Where resources allow, use ELIF or other AEIDL channels to monitor relevant policy developments and organise follow-up exchanges, webinars or policy updates.
Low use of the CSA Policy Toolkit (KER6)	Policy makers and policy advisors may not use the toolkit dashboard if they are unaware of it, if it is not intuitive, or if they lack time and capacity to explore it.	Carry out targeted communication to early adopters, such as Managing Authorities, policy advisors and CAP-related networks. Provide short explanations, demonstrations or user guidance showing how the dashboard can support policy design, implementation and evaluation.	Provide a “Toolkit Support session” coordinated by AEIDL Rural Territorial Development Unit to provide ad hoc guidance and maintain user engagement after the project through the ELIF.
Limited reuse of the EU Multi-Actor Working Group approach (KER3)	The co-creation and policy-learning approach may not be reused if the methodology is not clearly documented or promoted.	Ensure that the stakeholder mapping, workshop methodology, materials and lessons learned are documented and accessible. Present the Working Group as a replicable Science-Society-Policy model.	Integrate the approach into future ELIF training, policy-learning workshops, EU-funded projects or communities of practice.
Outputs become outdated due to	EU agricultural and food policy is evolving quickly.	Link recommendations to broader behavioural,	Provide light updates through blogs, webinars,

the changing policy context

Some recommendations may need updating over time.

systemic and governance challenges that remain relevant across policy cycles.

consultation inputs or future projects.

Low awareness of available outputs

End-users may not know how to access policy recommendations, briefs, workshop materials or the CSA Policy Toolkit after the project ends.

Ensure open access via the BEATLES website, the policy toolkit dashboard, Zenodo, other relevant repositories, and AEIDL channels.
Disseminate outputs through CAP Network channels and partners' networks.

The AEIDL website, which integrates both current and past projects, will continue to host BEATLES as a completed project, while ensuring that all materials produced remain accessible.
Any future activities or news related to BEATLES will be highlighted and echoed through the ELIF portal, ensuring ongoing visibility and engagement with the project's legacy.

Limited resources for post-project maintenance

Limited staff time and funding may restrict the ability to update materials, policy recommendations and the policy dashboard, maintain active engagement or organise new capacity-building activities.

Focus on low-maintenance sustainability mechanisms, including open repositories, the BEATLES website, AEIDL channels and the toolkit dashboard.

Seek opportunities under Horizon Europe, LIFE, Interreg or other EU programmes to continue or expand BEATLES-related policy-support work.
Reuse existing materials in future proposals and partnerships.

6. Conclusions: recommendations for further uptake

D5.3 has documented the mutual learning and capacity-building activities carried out through the EU Multi-Actor Working Group under Task 5.4. The activities reported in this deliverable show how BEATLES followed a progressive process, moving from stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement to workshop-based dialogue, feedback collection, output development and policy uptake. Through this process, BEATLES policy-oriented outputs were discussed, tested and translated into formats that can support policy learning, decision-making and future uptake by policy makers, policy advisors and other relevant stakeholders.

The EU Multi-Actor Working Group provided an incremental, iterative and adaptive process of engagement. The first workshop helped validate early BEATLES findings in relation to CAP reform and Climate-Smart Agriculture. The second workshop supported the co-design of policy options and recommendations through a policy hackathon format. The third workshop deepened the discussion on fairness in agri-food policy and explored how this concept can be translated into practical steps for policy design, implementation and evaluation. The final policy workshop connected the process more directly with future uptake by discussing how BEATLES policy recommendations and tools could inform current and upcoming EU policy instruments.

Together, these activities helped strengthen the capacity-building role of WP5. The use of various methodologies throughout the process (general conference format, working groups and hackathon) and the careful selection of participants specific for each of the focus topics of each meeting allowed a richer intake of reactions and perspective than a mere repetition of the same format four times. They helped identify key conditions for the uptake of Climate-Smart Agriculture, including long-term policy coherence, context-

specific measures, advisory support, stronger stakeholder participation, and the integration of fairness considerations into policy frameworks.

The deliverable also shows that capacity building does not depend only on workshops. Policy briefs, EU consultation inputs, stakeholder engagement, cross-work package exchanges, and synergies with EU initiatives also played an important role in translating BEATLES evidence into policy-relevant messages. These activities helped position BEATLES results within ongoing EU debates on the CAP, Farm to Fork, Biodiversity, climate action, fairness, simplification and future funding frameworks and the 2028–2034 EU programming period. Wider outreach through national CAP Networks, EU-level networks and multiplier organisations further increased the visibility and reach of BEATLES policy messages beyond the direct participants involved in the workshops.

From an exploitation perspective, D5.3 shows how WP5 capacity-building activities supported the co-creation, validation, feedback-based refinement, practical uptake and long-term sustainability of BEATLES policy outputs. While the formal exploitation strategy remains covered by D6.7, this deliverable demonstrates how the EU Multi-Actor Working Group helped connect BEATLES results with policy and advisory audiences, especially in relation to KER6 — Policy recommendations and tools.

A key legacy of this work is the CSA Tool Suite, available through the dedicated online platform www.climatesmartagri.eu. By bringing together the CSA Policy Toolkit, policy recommendations, recommendation fiches, policy briefs, use case-specific policy insights and other supporting resources, the platform provides a practical entry point for policy makers, Managing Authorities, paying agencies, governance bodies and technical assistance actors to use BEATLES results beyond the project lifetime.

To strengthen further uptake, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Keep BEATLES policy outputs accessible through the project website, AEIDL channels, repositories and other relevant platforms.
- Promote the CSA Policy Toolkit www.climatesmartagri.eu through practical demonstrations, webinars, training sessions and targeted exchanges with policy actors.
- Target early adopters and multiplier networks, including EU institutions, Managing Authorities, ministries, CAP Strategic Plan teams, advisory bodies, CAP/rural networks and EU-level initiatives.
- Use BEATLES outputs in post-2027 CAP discussions, future National and Regional Partnership Plans, EU consultations and related policy processes.
- Use future EU-funded projects to update and extend BEATLES results.
- Monitor examples of reuse where possible.

Overall, D5.3 shows that the EU Multi-Actor Working Group has acted as a bridge between BEATLES research outputs and their potential policy uptake. Its value lies not only in the workshops delivered, but also in the full process through which stakeholders were identified, engaged, consulted and informed, and through which project evidence were formulated into recommendations, tools and learning resources that can remain useful beyond the project lifetime. Continued uptake will depend on keeping these outputs accessible, targeted and connected to the evolving policy needs of European agri-food systems.

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² At the time of writing, D6.4 is not yet publicly available, as it is being finalised and submitted in parallel with D5.3. Once published, it will be accessible through the BEATLES project deliverables page: <https://beatles-project.eu/public-deliverables/page/2/>